

Development of a home service provider mobile application

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Abstract

A home service provider mobile application is a digital platform that connects customers with various service providers such as electricians, plumbers, cleaners, and other professionals who offer home-related services. This application allows users to search for a particular service they need, view service provider profiles and reviews, and book appointments in real-time. The app also provides a convenient payment system for hassle-free transactions. With the help of this application, users can easily find reliable and affordable service providers in their local area, allowing them to save time and effort while maintaining their home's upkeep. Overall, this app streamlines the process of finding home service providers, making it a valuable tool for homeowners and service providers alike.

Keywords: Home-related services; Mobile application; Digital platform; Home service provider; Online platform.

To cite this article:

Belacho, D. C., Gasangue, J. M. M., Flotibles, J. P. E., Malinis, E. A., Villareal, A. J. T., & Virata, A. J. A. (2023). Development of a home service provider mobile application. *SDCA Journal of Information Technology*, 7, 7-18.

Introduction

The present generation is the greatest user of online home services as well as the largest consumer of the Internet. With the advancement of technology, almost everything has changed, including the way people live, cook, shop, and date. Incentivizing clients to choose on-demand services will accelerate the industry's development in the next few years. The on-demand industry's expansion is also being fueled by the fast-expanding smartphone market, which enables clients to access information and book services (Goyal et al., 2017). According to Kaur (2021), the comfort and simplicity of access have resulted in a surge in the creation of on-demand home service apps in the market. People have stressful lives, as people lack the time necessary to locate a handyman when the need arises. Rather than having a hard and time-consuming way of trying to find a handyman to work for them, people prefer an app that can rapidly locate and contact a handyman.

Indeed, the rise of the home services business has been aided by online and mobile booking. Customers may easily select the correct provider to take care of any home service requirements with the simplicity of making appointments via businesses such as Google and Amazon Home Services (Lee & Lee, 2020). This new generation of on-demand app-based services simplifies people's lives. Users may get desired services with just a few clicks on their smartphone. On-demand business services are a result of new-age technologies. The creative expression of technology progress in relation to consumer behavior contributes to the on-demand app revolution (Kaur, 2020).

Household earnings have continued to climb as employment rates have increased in the aftermath of the global economic slump. Individuals with less time to devote to domestic activities and the financial resources to pay for domestic assistance via the home services sector are able to do so. Consumer expenditure on domestic services such as laundry, housekeeping, and gardening continues to increase as consumers and the economy recover from the recession. The on-demand economy has produced a whole new class of employees that fall halfway between self-employment and employment with a particular corporation. This part was formed because of inefficiencies caused by mismatches between required services and available resources. On-demand services are services that clients may choose and get from the comfort of their own homes. As the name says, it serves as a platform for the clients to hire specialists for all household duties and is equipped with all the necessary capabilities, just like all other requests. It is used to bridge the divide between consumers and service providers (Jain, 2021).

Miles and Boden (2001) agree that service-based companies are sometimes the simplest and cheapest to start, particularly if someone already possesses the necessary skills and equipment to offer the service. In contrast to other companies, personal services are those provided directly to customers. Offering personal services is not always as profitable or consistent as providing them to corporations. Having said that, many sectors, such as childcare, are resilient to economic downturns. Consumers often seek personal services due to convenience, time savings, or increased assistance for a number of reasons. When determining an acceptable level of service, each case must be evaluated on its own merits, considering the unique circumstances of each customer. This implies that in circumstances when more frequent services are reasonable, a higher level of service may be allowed (Clik, 2021).

According to Witsø et al. (2015), the home services industry directly benefits people's lives. Consumers may benefit from cleaner, better planned, more contemporary, and problem-free houses; and for experts, the industry provides a variety of well-paying employment options, providing millions of individuals with a solid source of income that rewards technical proficiency. With the advanced technology available today, it has been simpler than imagined for businesses to continue operating remotely. As a result, an increasing number of businesses are either extending their time away from their workplaces or eliminating office space completely. The percentage of people who work from home is expected to remain greater post-pandemic than it was previously, implying a sustained focus on the need to have a pleasant, efficient home. As a result, investing in the home services market is more appealing than ever.

Mobile applications assist administrators in alerting users of their interest in certain offers and items. Mobile application development is no longer seen as a means of remaining competitive. With broad use, apps have evolved into a tool for staying competitive and avoiding falling behind. As an entrepreneur or owner of a small company, one must not overlook the importance of mobile applications for business growth and development (Barnes, 2021).

With the advent of high-speed internet connections at much lower prices and the availability of smartphones with critical functionality, they have become a critical component of sustained corporate income creation (Omsoftware, 2019). One of the primary advantages of having a mobile app is that it can deliver all of the information that it wants to the consumers—including special deals and promotions—directly to the smartphones. Through push notifications, it can bring clients even closer to a direct engagement and simply remind the clients about goods and services at the appropriate times (Gavilan & Martin-Navarro, 2022).

Furthermore, mobile applications provide companies with an unparalleled chance to deliver a personalized user experience that not only strengthens ties with current consumers but also enables them to reach a larger market than ever before (Open Access Government, 2021). When companies' mobile apps are vulnerable, or when users' devices and personal information are hacked as a result of security flaws in mobile devices or applications, the repercussions may be catastrophic. Businesses may incur harm to their image and brand, as well as regulatory penalties; customers may become victims of identity theft or other forms of fraud. The good news is that by integrating mobile application security solutions, security issues involving a mobile device or app may be prevented entirely (LaSala, 2020).

In response to Rutherford's (2022), it was argued that digital transformation is a key factor in the long-term development and success of the business world, as it facilitates the optimization of a multitude of processes, the automatization of various activities, and the facilitation of remote work, thus simplifying the standard of living. This, in turn, provides a path to the top of the market. According to Lee et al. (2019), business technology allows businesses to expand their global reach. Globalization has been the result of technological breakthroughs, as any individual can now conduct business globally. E-commerce has seen a surge in recent years, which has contributed to the development of corporate globalization. Information technology has also reduced the costs and intricacies of production networks, which have been a key factor in economic globalization. Furthermore, the high speed of global communications has facilitated real-time trade and collaboration, thus contributing to the growth of international trade. These technological advances are leading to a variety of changes in our cultural and labor markets, which are transforming the way we conduct business.

Everyone had difficulties finding a job as a consequence of the current COVID-19 pandemic's long-term limitations, with unemployment predicted to be at its highest level since 2016. The economic recovery of the Philippines continues to be dependent on the growth and recovery of the digital economy and e-commerce sector. The pandemic has had a significant impact on the country's e-commerce sector, with lockdown measures affecting both traditional and new businesses alike. As a result, the Philippines has recognized the essential role of the e-commerce sector and digital economy as engines of economic growth and recovery. The surge in e-commerce activity in the country occurred during the peak of the outbreak, when most conventional retail stores were forced to close and citizens were forced to live in quarantine. The digital transformation of Filipinos' lives is becoming increasingly digital. The market's behavior has changed significantly, not only due to mobility restrictions but also due to the convenience gained through internet shopping (Chiu et al., 2017).

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to develop a Home Service Provider mobile application that addresses the issue about the COVID-19 lockdown that affected everyone, especially to those who are still afraid of going outside and to those who are working in the service industry which led to conceptualization, design, and development of a system that would benefit both the customers and skilled workers. However, this study specifically aims to:

1. Define the essential features of the mobile application that would address the concerns of customers and skilled workers.
2. Create a user-friendly and intuitive interface that allows customers to easily browse and book home services while considering their concerns about COVID-19 safety measures.
3. Develop the mobile application using appropriate programming languages and frameworks, ensuring compatibility across multiple platforms (Android).
4. Test the application under different scenarios to ensure its stability and performance, considering various device types and network conditions.
5. Deploy the application to relevant app stores and ensure a smooth installation and update process for end-users.
6. Conduct code review to manage defect on code development which includes prioritizing those defects that will invalidate the system's functions.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Input-Process-Output

This project is an opportunity to provide an efficient way of providing and receiving services. This research that is being conducted would contribute to all job seekers and consumers, especially in this modern times. The programming language that was used is Java Language. The process of delivering this project includes brainstorming of the researcher and analyzing if it would fit the project. There is a need for recalling code and past projects for creating a mobile application system, it enables the researcher to be reminded of how a system is developed.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a developmental research design that combines experimental and descriptive methods to direct the development of a mobile application for home service providers. While the experimental component dealt with the system’s actual design, development, and testing, the descriptive component concentrated on determining user demands, system requirements, and usability expectations. By using this method, the program was guaranteed to be both functional and in line with user requirements and actual usage scenarios.

System Development Approach

The Agile Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC), which prioritizes gradual modifications, continuous feedback, and iterative development, was used in the study. Throughout the development process, the researchers were able to ensure flexibility and response to user feedback by refining system features over time. The main issue that the researchers discovered during the planning stage was the challenge of finding trustworthy home service providers. Target users were selected, objectives were well-defined, and SWOT analysis was used to assess viability. Hardware and software requirements were also established to properly direct the development process.

The system requirements were gathered and examined in this analysis phase according to the service providers' and customers' needs. User registration, service browsing, booking, chat capabilities, and review systems were listed as functional needs. To guarantee system quality, non-functional requirements were also developed, such as security, usability, performance, and compatibility. Using the Model-View-Controller (MVC) framework, the design phase concentrated on developing the system architecture and user interface. Creating user-friendly interfaces for the chat module, booking system, home page, and profile management was part of this phase. Additionally, system flowcharts were made to illustrate data flow and user interactions inside the program, and database structures were constructed using an Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD).

Firestore was used as the database for real-time data management in the Java application created in Android Studio. User login with OTP verification, service provider registration with ID validation, search and filtering tools, booking administration, messaging systems, ratings, and reviews were among the key features put in place. Iterative cycles were used in the development process to enable ongoing feature enhancement and improvement. To guarantee the system's functionality and dependability, extensive testing was conducted. While integration testing made sure that modules interacted properly, unit testing was used to confirm individual components. User acceptance testing used actual individuals to evaluate usability, whereas system testing assessed overall functionality. To guarantee system resilience, testing was done on various devices and network scenarios.

The application was ready for deployment following successful testing. This involved writing the required user documentation, making sure the application was compatible with all Android devices, and packaging it for installation. A seamless and convenient installation process was the goal of the deployment procedure. Following deployment, the system was continuously monitored and improved during the maintenance phase. This involved implementing user comments, improving performance, updating functionality, and correcting bugs. The Agile methodology facilitates continuous upgrades, guaranteeing the application's continued relevance and effectiveness. The system has a client-server architecture, with Firestore acting as the backend server for data synchronization and storage and the mobile application acting as the client interface. Real-time updates, effective data management, and system scalability are made possible by this architecture.

Data Gathering and Evaluation

The respondents consisted of 100 participants, including 80 end-users such as customers and service providers, and 20 expert users from the IT industry. Majority of the end users are customers and service workers in which the researchers conducted system testing for days before proceeding to the software evaluation. On the other hand, other respondents are voluntary in which the end and expert users can freely test the system since the access is provided on the software evaluation. This distribution ensured a balanced evaluation from both general users and technical professionals.

The system was evaluated using a structured questionnaire based on the ISO 9126 software quality standard. Functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability were among the evaluation criteria. The respondents' degree of agreement and pleasure was measured using a five-point Likert scale. To ascertain overall satisfaction levels, statistical tools such as mean and percentage distribution were used to examine the gathered data. The instrument's dependability was further assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, which produced an outstanding internal consistency score of 0.92.

The mobile application was made available to respondents, who were then free to experiment with its features. They finished the evaluation questionnaire after utilizing the system. The efficacy of the system in terms of usability, performance, and general user satisfaction was then ascertained by analyzing the data.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Evaluation of the System's Design

	DESIGN	End Users		Expert Users	
		MEAN	REMARKS	MEAN	REMARKS
1.	End-Users: The system presents a new and fresh perspective on the intended purpose. Expert Users: The system has an appropriate GUI that was used in the system. (Originality)	4.50	Strongly Agree	4.60	Strongly Agree
2.	End-Users: The system is well-organized and has easy-to-use user interface. Expert Users: The system meets the basic method of minimalist design on user interface. (Simplicity)	4.80	Strongly Agree	4.60	Strongly Agree
3.	End-Users: The colors, designs, and organization of GUI are pleasing to the eye. Expert Users: The system's visual design does not distract from its functionality and purpose. (Aesthetics)	4.80	Strongly Agree	4.80	Strongly Agree
4.	End-Users: The system's layout is clear and intuitive. Expert Users: The system can optimize different resolutions. (Visibility)	4.70	Strongly Agree	4.53	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean		4.70	Strongly Agree	4.63	Strongly Agree

Table 1 shows the evaluation response in the design. The data shows that the end users conceded that the simplicity and aesthetics of the system got the remarks of Strongly Agree with the mean of 4.8. This is because the system's use of pleasing colors and designs is well-organized and has easy-to-use user interface. In contrast, originality is the least, which got 4.5 as Strongly Agree. This is because the system has almost the same perspective as the other benchmark service mobile application that exists already, while overall mean of the system's design is 4.7. This is because the system meets the basic requirements to have a friendly-user user interface.

Meanwhile, expert users conceded that the aesthetics of the system got the remarks of Strongly Agree with the mean of 4.8. This is because the system's visual design does not distract from its purpose. In contrast, visibility is the least, which got 4.53 as Strongly Agree. Despite this, the system does not see any resolution issues for different android devices, while the overall mean of the system's design is 4.63. This is because the system meets the basic requirements to have a friendly user interface.

Table 2 shows the evaluation response in the functionality. The data shows that the end users conceded that the suitability of the system got the remarks of Strongly Agree with the mean of 4.8. This is because the system can produce accurate tasks assigned. In contrast, originality is the least, which got 4.5 as Strongly Agree. This is because the system is new and only has few to connect with the other system, while the overall mean of the system's functionality is 4.64. This is because the system can provide the end users' desired functionalities.

On the other hand, expert users conceded that the suitability of the system got the remarks of Strongly Agree with the mean of 4.9. This is because the system can accurately perform the intended tasks and its functions. In contrast, interoperability is the least, which got 4.35 as Agree. This is because the system is new and needs improvement so that it can interact with other applications, while the overall mean of the system's functionality is 4.73. This is because the system can be installed, deployed, and accessed easily using different types of Android devices.

Table 2. Evaluation of the System's Functionality

FUNCTIONALITY	End Users		Expert Users	
	MEAN	REMARKS	MEAN	REMARKS
1. End-Users: The system provides an accurate result on the search navigation. Expert Users: The system can accurately perform the intended tasks and their functionality. (Accuracy)	4.60	Strongly Agree	4.90	Strongly Agree
2. End-Users: The system can produce the accurate task assigned. Expert Users: The system's various functions are well-integrated. (Suitability)	4.80	Strongly Agree	4.80	Strongly Agree
3. End-Users: The system can work together with other systems. Expert Users: The system module responds to the specific function intended for its purpose. (Interoperability)	4.50	Strongly Agree	4.35	Agree
4. End-Users: The system requires user to have a password and an authentication when creating and updating an account. Expert Users: The system has robust security features to protect user data and ensure privacy. (Security)	4.70	Strongly Agree	4.80	Strongly Agree
5. End-Users: The system is consistent in providing the user's needs. Expert Users: The structure of the system has a fair functional consistency. (Functionality Compliance)	4.60	Strongly Agree	4.80	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.64	Strongly Agree	4.73	Strongly Agree

Table 3. Evaluation of the System's Usability

USABILITY	End Users		Expert Users	
	MEAN	REMARKS	MEAN	REMARKS
1. End-Users: The system does not require extensive training or technical expertise. Expert Users: The system has well-designed onboarding process to quickly understand the app's features and functions. (Learnability)	4.60	Strongly Agree	4.80	Strongly Agree
2. End-Users: The system is easy to manage. Expert Users: The system can provide contextual help and guidance to end-users. (Understandability)	4.42	Agree	4.25	Agree
3. End-Users: The system has intuitive user interface design with clear terminology and icons. Expert Users: The system meets the basic requirements for designing the GUI. (User-Friendliness)	4.80	Strongly Agree	4.90	Strongly Agree
4. End-Users: The system can maximize the use of the users' inputs to produce outputs. Expert Users: The system is easy to manage and less complex. (Operational Effectiveness)	4.71	Strongly Agree	4.70	Strongly Agree
5. The system is user-friendly and visually appealing to users. (Attractiveness)	4.62	Strongly Agree	4.80	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.63	Strongly Agree	4.69	Strongly Agree

Table 3 shows the evaluation response in terms of usability. The data shows that the end-users conceded that the user-friendliness of the system got the remarks of Strongly Agree with the mean of 4.8. This is because the system has intuitive user interface design with clear terminology and icons. In contrast, understandability is the least, which got 4.42 as Agree. This is because the system is new and still needs constant use to understand how it fully works, while the overall mean of the system's usability is 4.63. This is because the system can provide the end users' desired functionalities.

Meanwhile, expert users conceded that the user-friendliness of the system got the remarks of Strongly Agree with the mean of 4.9. This is because the system meets the basic requirements for designing

the GUI. In contrast, understandability is the least, which got 4.25 as Agree. This is because the system has limited contextual help and guidance to help end-users to how the application works, while the overall mean of the system's usability is 4.69. This is because the system can be understood, learned, and used easily.

Table 4. Evaluation of the System's Efficiency

EFFICIENCY		End Users		Expert Users	
		MEAN	REMARKS	MEAN	REMARKS
1.	End-Users: The system has an acceptable response to process users' request. Expert Users: The system has an acceptable latency to process operations. (Timeliness)	4.63	Strongly Agree	4.80	Strongly Agree
2.	End-Users: The system can comply with the users' needs as quickly as possible. Expert Users: The system has fast enough response to end-users' request. (Efficiency Compliance)	4.52	Strongly Agree	4.60	Strongly Agree
3.	End-Users: The system can be easily used with minimum requirements. Expert Users: The least possible requirements can function smoothly. (Resource Utilization)	4.70	Strongly Agree	4.90	Strongly Agree
4.	End-Users: The system's loading times is acceptable. Expert Users: The system's overall speed and performance meets the expectations. (Time Behavior)	4.43	Agree	4.80	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean		4.57	Strongly Agree	4.78	Strongly Agree

Table 4 shows the evaluation response in the efficiency. The data shows that the end users conceded that the resource utilization of the system got the remarks of Strongly Agree with the mean of 4.7. This is because the system can be easily used with the minimum requirements. In contrast, time behavior is the least, which got 4.43 as Agree. This is because the system can still experience some delays with the system's loading, while the overall mean of the system's usability is 4.57. This is because the system provides performance in accordance to the resources used by the end users.

Meanwhile, expert users conceded that the resource utilization of the system got the remarks of Strongly Agree with the mean of 4.9. This is because the system can function smoothly with least possible requirements. In contrast, efficiency utilization is the least, which got 4.6 as Strongly Agree. Despite this, the system was satisfied enough with how fast enough the system responds with the end-users' request, while the overall mean of the system's efficiency is 4.77. This is because the system provides performance in accordance to the resources used or available.

Table 5 shows the evaluation response in the maintainability. The data shows that the respondents conceded that the changeability of the system got the remarks of Strongly Agree with the mean of 4.7. This is because the system is capable to handle dynamic changes. In contrast, maintainability compliance is the least, which got 4.42 as Agree. This is because the system cannot notify the end-users for further updates of the system, while the overall mean of the system's maintainability is 4.55. This is because the system can be easily well-maintained.

Meanwhile, the expert users conceded that the testability of the system got the remarks of Strongly Agree with the mean of 4.9. This is because the system can respond accordingly and operates safely. In contrast, analyzability is the least, which got 4.3 as Agree. This is because the system has no provision to notify degree of error, while the overall mean of the system's maintainability is 4.7. This is because the system can be easily well-maintained.

Table 5. Evaluation of the System's Maintainability

	MAINTAINABILITY	End Users		Expert Users	
		MEAN	REMARKS	MEAN	REMARKS
1.	End-Users: The system was easy to use and responsive. Expert Users: The system responds accordingly and operates safely. (Testability)	4.53	Strongly Agree	4.90	Strongly Agree
2.	End-Users: The system provides a notification error to users upon unnecessary process. Expert Users: The system has provision to notify degree of error during the unnecessary process. (Analyzability)	4.50	Strongly Agree	4.30	Agree
3.	End-Users: The system is capable to handle dynamic changes. Expert Users: The system can alter its state to meet new requirements and expectations. (Changeability)	4.70	Strongly Agree	4.80	Strongly Agree
4.	End-Users: The system performs reliably and consistently under normal operating conditions. Expert Users: The system is capable to maintain or restore its equilibrium. (Stability)	4.60	Strongly Agree	4.70	Strongly Agree
5.	End-Users: The system can notify the users for further updates of the system. Expert Users: The system has a well-structured, modular, and well-documented code of application. (Maintainability Compliance)	4.42	Agree	4.73	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean		4.55	Strongly Agree	4.69	Strongly Agree

Table 6 shows the evaluation response in the portability. The data shows that the respondents conceded that the accessibility of the system got the remarks of Strongly Agree with the mean of 4.8. This is because the system can be accessed from different types of android devices. In contrast, adaptability is the least, which got 4.61 as Strongly Agree. Despite this, the system could still gather feedback from both the end users and service providers, but end users can still give feedback and reviews to service providers, while the overall mean of the system's portability is 4.68. This is because the system can be installed, deployed, and accessed easily using different types of Android devices.

Table 6. Evaluation of the System's Portability

	PORTABILITY	End Users		Expert Users	
		MEAN	REMARKS	MEAN	REMARKS
1.	End-Users: The system can accurately perform the intended tasks and their functionality. Expert Users: The system can adapt and meet the changing needs and preferences of end-users. (Accuracy)	4.90	Strongly Agree	4.50	Strongly Agree
2.	End-Users: The system's various functions are well-integrated. Expert Users: The system meets industry best practices accessibility standards for every type of android devices. (Suitability)	4.80	Strongly Agree	4.90	Strongly Agree
3.	End-Users: The system module responds to the specific function intended for its purpose. Expert Users: The system can move, copy or transfer personal data easily from one IT environment to another in a safe and secure way, without affecting its usability. (Interoperability)	4.35	Agree	4.80	Strongly Agree
4.	End-Users: The system has robust security features to protect user data and ensure privacy. Expert Users: The system is capable to be accessed by multiple users and android devices simultaneously. (Security)	4.80	Strongly Agree	4.80	Strongly Agree
5.	End-Users: The structure of the system has a fair functional consistency. Expert Users: The limit of the system to fill in according to standards, guidelines, and rules relevant to the system. (Portability Compliance)	4.80	Strongly Agree	4.40	Agree
Overall Mean		4.73	Strongly Agree	4.68	Strongly Agree

Meanwhile, the expert users conceded that the accessibility of the system got the remarks of Strongly Agree with the mean of 4.9. This is because the system meets industry best practices accessibility standards for every type of android devices. In contrast, portability compliance is the least, which got 4.4 as Agree. This is because the system has no limit to full in according to commensurate standards, shows guidelines and rules relevant to the system, while the overall mean of the system’s portability is 4.7. This is because the system is capable of being ported from environment to another.

Table 7. Overall Level of Satisfaction Based on Respondent’s Distribution

Category	End User	Expert User	Overall Rating	Rating
Design	4.70	4.63	4.67	Strongly Agree
Functionality	4.64	4.73	4.69	Strongly Agree
Usability	4.63	4.70	4.67	Strongly Agree
Efficiency	4.57	4.78	4.68	Strongly Agree
Maintainability	4.55	4.77	4.66	Strongly Agree
Portability	4.73	4.68	4.71	Strongly Agree
Average	4.64	4.72	4.68	Strongly Agree

In Table 7, the level of satisfaction and respondent frequency are used to display the overall response of the expert-users and end-users. The level of satisfaction experienced by both expert users and end users is ‘strongly agree’, with a mean score of 4.65.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researchers were able to conclude that the specific objectives outlined for the development of the home service provider mobile application highlight the importance of addressing customer and skilled worker concerns, creating a user-friendly interface, ensuring compatibility and performance, deploying the application effectively, and conducting code review to manage defects.

These objectives collectively contribute to the successful implementation of the application and the realization of its intended benefits. By defining essential features that cater to the needs of customers and skilled workers, the application can effectively address their concerns, fostering trust and convenience. The creation of a user-friendly and intuitive interface enhances the user experience, enabling easy browsing and booking of home services while considering COVID-19 safety measures.

Developing the application using appropriate technologies and ensuring compatibility across multiple platforms facilitates widespread usage. Thorough testing of the application under different scenarios guarantees stability and performance across various devices and network conditions. Deploying the application to relevant app stores and streamlining the installation and update process ensures a seamless experience for end-users.

Lastly, conducting code review helps manage defects, prioritize critical issues, and safeguard the system’s overall functionality. These specific objectives collectively contribute to the successful development and deployment of the Home Service Provider mobile application, ultimately benefiting both customers and skilled workers.

The project shows that it serves a Home Service Provider mobile application system that provide users with access to various home services from the convenience of their smartphones should do for future plans of system are location-gathering feature, chat support agent, and mode of payment.

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